

Prof. Fariz Khalilli PhD, prof. Kubra Aliveva PhD, Faig Nasibov, Sakina Baghirova , Imran Rahimov, Institute of Archaeology and Anthropology, Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences

Digital Reconstruction and Unified Database of Glazed Ceramic Fragments (11th–14th Centuries) Found at the Haji Badal Mosque in the Basqal Settlement, Azerbaijan (HKR-MB Project)

From 26 August to 24 September 2025, the Institute of Archaeology and Anthropology of the Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences conducted archaeological excavations at the Haji Badal Mosque in the Basqal settlement (Ismayilli District) under the supervision of Dr. Fariz Khalilli (PhD in History). The fieldwork was carried out in two excavation trenches in parallel with restoration activities in the mosque courtyard.

The investigation revealed traces of multi-layered historical development. The site functioned as a residential area during the 11th–13th centuries under the Shirvanshah dynasty, was later reused for domestic purposes, and subsequently transformed into a mosque courtyard built by Haji Badal in the 1850s. During the Soviet period, the area was repurposed as a storage facility.

A total of 298 artifacts - including ceramic fragments, metal objects, coins, and animal bones - were documented, reflecting the economic and cultural dynamics of medieval Basqal. Architectural remains such as a two-phase riverstone pavement, drainage channel, water well, and column bases were also uncovered, attesting to the religious, domestic, and utilitarian functions of the site.

Building on these findings, the HKR-MB Project aims to digitally reconstruct the glazed ceramic fragments dated to the 11th–14th centuries and to create a unified scientific database integrating visual, typological, and descriptive data. The project focuses on the digital restoration of ornamental motifs, their systematic documentation, and open accessibility for researchers and the general public.

This initiative contributes to the digital preservation of Azerbaijan's medieval ceramic heritage, promotes interdisciplinary collaboration between archaeology and information technologies, and establishes a sustainable framework for cultural memory in the digital age. The HKR-MB database will serve as a vital platform for scientific research, education, and heritage communication.

Keywords: Basqal Settlement; Haji Badal Mosque; Glazed Ceramics; Digital Reconstruction; Database; Archaeology; Azerbaijan.

Center for Advanced Research, Skopje, North Macedonia

Aydin Adnan Menderes University, Turkiye

MIRAS Social Organization in Support of Studying of
Cultural Heritage, Baku, Azerbaijan

&

Institute for film- Film Academy, Ohrid, North Macedonia

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- BOOK OF ABSTRACTS –

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